

Density and viscosity of ternary liquid mixtures of pyridine with some polar and non-polar solvents at 303.15 K

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Density and viscosity of ternary liquid mixtures of pyridine with some polar (acetone and methyl ethyl ketone) and non-polar (benzene, toluene and carbon tetrachloride) solvents have been measured as a function of the composition and at a constant temperature 303.15 K. Various excess thermodynamic functions, viz. excess viscosity (η^E), excess volume (V^E), excess Gibbs free energy of activation of flow (ΔG^{*E}) and the values of interaction parameter d in Grunberg and Nissan equation have been calculated as a function of composition of ternary mixtures. The results have been interpreted in terms of molecular interactions existing between the components of these mixtures.

Pyridine has a stable structure of benzene, which has a lone-pair of electrons as well as the π -electrons. Its structure is such that if it provides a negative charge on one side, it can provide the positive charge at the other end. Some workers^{1,2} have studied the structural behavior of pyridine in detail and have suggested the self-association among its own molecules. Hence, it follows that if the other unlike molecules want to interact with pyridine then they have to overcome these weak forces of interaction. Only two molecules of pyridine are associated with each other and the association is thus limited to dimer.

In the light of the above nature of the molecule of pyridine it was thought worthwhile to undertake viscometric studies on the molecular interactions in the ternary liquid mixtures involving pyridine as the first component, and some polar solvents as the second component and non-polar solvents as the third component.

Results and Discussion

The values of density (ρ), viscosity (η), molar volume (V) and excess thermodynamic functions, viz. the excess viscosity (η^E), the excess molar volume (V^E) and the excess Gibbs free energy of activation of flow (ΔG^{*E}) and the interaction parameter (d) have been calculated as a function of composition of the ternary liquid mixtures as discussed below.

The excess viscosity (η^E) of a given ternary liquid mixture has been evaluated from the observed viscosity of the mixture and that of its pure components using the equation,

$$\eta^E = \eta - (x_1\eta_1 + x_2\eta_2 + x_3\eta_3) \quad (1)$$

where η is the viscosity of ternary liquid mixture, and η_1 ,

η_2 and η_3 are the viscosities and x_1 , x_2 and x_3 are the mole fractions of components 1, 2 and 3, respectively. The excess molar volume (V^E) of the ternary liquid mixtures has been evaluated from the molar volume of the mixtures (V) and that of the pure components (V_1 , V_2 and V_3) using the equation,

$$V^E = V - (x_1V_1 + x_2V_2 + x_3V_3) \quad (2)$$

The molar volume (V) of the ternary liquid mixture has been calculated from the measured density (ρ) of mixture using the equation,

$$V = (x_1M_1 + x_2M_2 + x_3M_3)/\rho \quad (3)$$

where x_1 , x_2 and x_3 are the mole fractions of the components 1, 2 and 3 of the ternary liquid mixtures, respectively, V_1 is M_1/ρ_1 , V_2 is M_2/ρ_2 and V_3 is M_3/ρ_3 , ρ_1 , ρ_2 and ρ_3 are the densities of the components 1, 2 and 3 of the ternary liquid mixtures, respectively.

The excess Gibbs free energy of activation of flow (ΔG^{*E}), for the ternary liquid mixture has been computed from the Eyring equation³,

$$\Delta G^{*E} = [RT \{ \ln \eta V - (x_1 \ln \eta_1 V_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2 V_2 + x_3 \ln \eta_3 V_3) \}] \quad (4)$$

where the letters have their usual significance.

Grunberg and Nissan⁴ suggested a logarithm relation between the viscosity of a binary liquid mixture and that of its pure components.

$$\ln \eta = x_1 \ln \eta_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2 + x_1 x_2 d \quad (5)$$

On applying to a ternary liquid mixture, this equation takes up the form,

$$\ln \eta = x_1 \ln \eta_1 + x_2 \ln \eta_2 + x_3 \ln \eta_3 + x_1 x_2 x_3 d \quad (6)$$

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Table 1. Values of density, viscosity and excess thermodynamic properties for ternary liquid mixtures of pyridine with some polar and non-polar solvents at 303.15 K

x_1	x_2	ρ g cm ⁻³	η mpa s	η^E mPa s	V cm ³ mol ⁻¹	V^E cm ³ mol ⁻¹	d	ΔG^{FE} J mol ⁻¹
Pyridine (1) + acetone (2) + benzene (3)								
0.0475	0.7805	0.8084	0.3598	-0.0197	77.3424	-0.4253	-0.5067	-15.0225
0.0970	0.6853	0.8233	0.3834	-0.0342	78.3183	-0.5079	-1.1345	-49.5964
0.1471	0.5883	0.8368	0.4138	-0.0425	79.4359	-0.4720	-0.7923	-51.8965
0.1558	0.2828	0.8589	0.4883	-0.0467	84.5264	-0.1243	-1.4520	-85.3535
0.1985	0.4879	0.8505	0.4420	-0.0543	80.5739	-0.4501	-1.0835	-87.1137
0.2523	0.3845	0.8646	0.4772	-0.0606	81.7303	-0.4581	-1.1175	-105.4859
0.2597	0.2259	0.8734	0.5254	-0.0540	84.5458	-0.0715	-1.3140	-94.3612
0.3069	0.2786	0.8781	0.5193	-0.0607	82.9444	-0.4182	-1.1315	-105.8240
0.3341	0.3645	0.8722	0.5028	-0.0637	81.5637	-0.1996	-0.9061	-82.2683
0.3629	0.1701	0.8921	0.5681	-0.0552	84.1410	-0.4318	-1.3024	-100.9593
0.4666	0.1133	0.9069	0.6149	-0.0528	84.1356	-0.4040	-1.5854	-95.4077
0.5104	0.1674	0.9074	0.5988	-0.0681	82.9428	-0.3505	-1.7532	-126.6429
0.5538	0.2194	0.9088	0.5886	-0.0780	81.7162	-0.3675	-1.9245	-139.6921
0.5589	0.1666	0.9099	0.6111	-0.0702	82.7916	-0.0871	-1.9000	-120.7975
0.5955	0.2702	0.9112	0.5800	-0.0861	80.4296	-0.4787	-2.5607	-149.9957
0.6480	0.2170	0.9177	0.6111	-0.0836	81.0840	-0.2007	-2.9621	-144.8753
0.6881	0.2678	0.9191	0.5976	-0.0961	79.8903	-0.2259	-8.0755	-169.6987
Pyridine (1) + acetone (2) + toluene (3)								
0.0488	0.8031	0.8084	0.3594	-0.0089	79.3472	-0.6566	-9.1007	52.0290
0.1006	0.7105	0.8233	0.3830	-0.0218	80.9286	-0.7991	-6.0795	27.5659
0.1537	0.6149	0.8368	0.4077	-0.0347	82.6867	-0.8231	-5.2851	-1.8222
0.1715	0.3113	0.8589	0.4786	-0.0331	92.3283	-0.8531	-9.3864	-5.3343
0.2092	0.5141	0.8505	0.4379	-0.0439	84.5406	-0.8613	-4.8838	-19.7637
0.2681	0.4088	0.8646	0.4725	-0.0508	86.4150	-0.9314	-4.9472	-37.7885
0.2835	0.2465	0.8734	0.5138	-0.0486	91.6503	-0.7174	-7.7255	-48.7609
0.3292	0.2987	0.8781	0.5124	-0.0542	88.4563	-0.9515	-5.5894	-53.0299
0.3514	0.3832	0.8722	0.4909	-0.0654	85.4297	-0.5714	-4.5552	-73.1843
0.3929	0.1840	0.8921	0.5537	-0.0580	90.5228	-1.0309	-7.9092	-89.4742
0.5009	0.1216	0.9069	0.5981	-0.0624	89.8297	-0.9289	-9.9221	-109.9068
0.5387	0.1766	0.9074	0.5873	-0.0742	87.1725	-0.7428	-7.0725	-129.0679
0.5751	0.2278	0.9088	0.5802	-0.0827	84.5971	-0.6391	-5.9138	-140.5859
0.5851	0.1744	0.9099	0.6003	-0.0771	86.3568	-0.4053	-7.0060	-127.8939
0.6088	0.2762	0.9112	0.5720	-0.0919	82.0892	-0.6408	-6.1307	-163.1780
0.6625	0.2220	0.9177	0.5993	-0.0937	82.7437	-0.3541	-7.4662	-173.2641
0.6931	0.2697	0.9191	0.5882	-0.1050	80.4285	-0.2764	-14.0428	-203.4835
Pyridine (1) + acetone (2) + carbon tetrachloride (3)								
0.0481	0.7910	0.9492	0.4000	-0.0231	78.4825	-0.3585	6.8975	108.3424
0.0987	0.6974	0.9978	0.4360	-0.0374	79.8517	-0.3453	2.4528	91.5000
0.1502	0.6008	1.0475	0.4787	-0.0467	81.2186	-0.3899	1.3739	82.8978
0.1630	0.2958	1.2803	0.6487	-0.0399	88.5111	-0.0554	1.1293	91.7757
0.2037	0.5004	1.0971	0.5293	-0.0500	82.6645	-0.4115	1.0129	82.4582
0.2597	0.3960	1.1474	0.5876	-0.0479	84.1000	-0.4884	0.8505	80.1240
0.2707	0.2355	1.2612	0.6894	-0.0320	88.0437	-0.1350	0.9279	87.8283
0.3172	0.2880	1.1936	0.6509	-0.0426	85.9081	-0.2597	0.6653	70.8417
0.3424	0.3735	1.1073	0.5954	-0.0526	83.5157	-0.2283	0.5611	60.2912
0.3766	0.1765	1.2413	0.7296	-0.0239	87.6358	-0.1694	0.8853	76.7710
0.4825	0.1172	1.2220	0.7729	-0.0129	87.1858	-0.2381	1.0542	67.5298
0.5239	0.1718	1.1504	0.7227	-0.0341	85.3843	-0.0719	0.4085	39.0275
0.5640	0.2234	1.0865	0.6800	-0.0494	83.1013	-0.4721	0.0627	1.1765
0.5712	0.1703	1.1503	0.7409	-0.0170	82.4441	-2.2576	1.3629	30.0578
0.6018	0.2731	1.0152	0.6325	-0.0075	81.4686	-0.3050	-1.0325	-54.5288
0.6549	0.2194	1.0154	0.6626	-0.0694	82.6083	0.4586	-1.5947	-50.7003
0.6903	0.2687	0.9575	0.6223	-0.0835	79.9117	-0.4876	-5.5796	-118.0539
Pyridine (1) + methy ethyl ketone (2) + benzene (3)								
0.0552	0.7448	0.8315	0.4208	-0.0160	88.6300	-1.8373	-0.7584	-66.6224
0.1106	0.6412	0.8436	0.4421	-0.0302	88.1606	-1.7472	-1.2586	-103.7976
0.1641	0.2445	0.8688	0.5309	-0.0311	88.3958	-0.7825	-0.9620	-76.8874
0.1644	0.5398	0.8533	0.4666	-0.0403	87.9339	-1.4301	-1.2171	-119.1175
0.2176	0.4387	0.8647	0.4908	-0.0505	87.5370	-1.2887	-1.3637	-147.0645

Table 1 (contd.)

0.2707	0.1931	0.8814	0.5653	-0.0374	87.6099	-0.5908	-0.9083	-78.3006
0.2710	0.3389	0.8746	0.5193	-0.0562	87.2912	-0.9953	-1.4294	-154.7341
0.3231	0.2406	0.8865	0.5540	-0.0551	86.8429	-0.9169	-1.4237	-144.9986
0.3575	0.3200	0.8832	0.5544	-0.0499	86.6666	-0.8331	-0.8051	-95.6046
0.3743	0.1440	0.8971	0.5906	-0.0515	86.5194	-0.7228	-1.7334	-131.0546
0.4763	0.0949	0.9087	0.6235	-0.0575	85.8503	-0.4479	-2.7580	-144.2777
0.5262	0.1416	0.9125	0.6247	-0.0621	85.2398	-0.6394	-2.1594	-149.9177
0.5761	0.1410	0.9186	0.6500	-0.0514	84.7315	-0.7001	-1.5181	-105.1016
0.5766	0.1873	0.9143	0.6213	-0.0716	84.8267	-0.6285	-2.4096	-169.8126
0.6259	0.2329	0.9161	0.6155	-0.0832	84.4225	-0.6276	-3.5370	-199.4984
0.6743	0.1853	0.9246	0.6408	-0.0809	83.9993	-0.5790	-4.1190	-196.0548
0.7228	0.2309	0.9262	0.6371	-0.0902	83.6029	-0.5592	-10.3477	-214.1747
Pyridine (1) + methyl ethyl ketone (2) + toluene (3)								
0.0571	0.7698	0.8201	0.4180	-0.0078	92.6515	-0.8758	1.2323	5.8110
0.1153	0.6682	0.8321	0.4404	-0.0196	92.8403	-0.8599	-0.0574	-16.4226
0.1728	0.5671	0.8437	0.4620	-0.0319	93.0754	-0.8169	-0.5886	-48.1798
0.2305	0.4647	0.8563	0.4899	-0.0381	93.2224	-0.8789	-0.5766	-56.9947
0.2893	0.3620	0.8669	0.5152	-0.0474	93.5626	-0.7144	-0.8675	-81.5493
0.3478	0.2590	0.8762	0.5395	-0.0576	94.0618	-0.4222	-1.3703	-114.6205
0.4063	0.1562	0.8864	0.5713	-0.0603	94.4499	-0.2376	-1.9490	-122.2962
0.5121	0.1020	0.8999	0.6123	-0.0623	92.6983	-0.0889	-2.7330	-118.8335
0.5563	0.1497	0.9026	0.6117	-0.0705	90.7239	-0.0754	-2.5324	-138.4659
0.5996	0.1949	0.9069	0.6079	-0.0820	88.6649	-0.2038	-3.1103	-176.7288
0.6406	0.2384	0.9092	0.6056	-0.0916	86.9101	-0.1455	-4.5439	-204.9703
0.7284	0.2326	0.9204	0.6352	-0.0919	84.7270	-0.0829	-12.3458	-201.8740
0.6900	0.1897	0.9178	0.6384	-0.0822	86.4409	-0.1118	-4.5736	-171.9360
0.6039	0.1479	0.9104	0.6426	-0.0556	89.2965	-0.2582	-1.6647	-80.9093
0.2966	0.2116	0.8755	0.5461	-0.0410	95.9840	-0.6690	-0.8713	-66.0083
0.1816	0.2705	0.8614	0.5136	-0.0268	97.9264	-0.7825	-0.4461	-34.3997
0.3773	0.3377	0.8765	0.5399	-0.0554	91.7922	-0.5669	-0.9965	-90.0877
Pyridine (1) + methyl ethyl ketone (2) + carbon tetrachloride (3)								
0.0561	0.7564	0.9646	0.4688	-0.0197	91.0458	-0.8705	3.6147	50.5968
0.1128	0.6542	1.0056	0.5029	-0.0342	91.4178	-0.2710	0.8628	34.1407
0.1683	0.5527	1.0555	0.5416	-0.0438	91.0244	-0.4611	0.2122	6.5711
0.1721	0.2563	1.2929	0.7032	-0.0225	92.8288	-0.7147	0.9504	46.9273
0.2237	0.4512	1.1042	0.5886	-0.0451	90.7719	-0.5119	0.1605	5.7031
0.2796	0.3497	1.1515	0.6410	-0.0410	90.6247	-0.4582	0.1981	12.2813
0.2827	0.2016	1.2703	0.7358	-0.0164	91.4990	-0.5967	0.8129	50.8187
0.3345	0.2491	1.1981	-0.7063	-0.0236	90.5368	-0.3464	0.6188	52.5097
0.3670	0.3285	1.1214	0.6647	-0.0278	88.7783	-0.9963	0.6971	43.7929
0.3889	0.1496	1.2458	0.7657	-0.0116	90.3336	-0.3503	0.7598	50.8117
0.4929	0.0982	1.2570	0.8282	0.0261	86.6878	-2.6259	2.8363	76.1018
0.5406	0.1455	1.1823	0.7761	-0.0039	85.8814	-2.2988	1.1991	17.0832
0.5876	0.1910	1.0881	0.7116	-0.0471	86.6655	-0.3965	-0.8168	53.8782
0.5892	0.1442	1.1272	0.7495	-0.0314	86.9521	-0.4259	-0.2928	-20.4323
0.6328	0.2356	1.0222	0.6660	-0.0719	85.3906	-0.6080	-2.5568	-137.9483
0.6818	0.1873	1.0334	0.7198	-0.0412	84.7413	-0.7833	-0.7380	-48.0502
0.7253	0.2316	0.9641	0.6689	-0.0713	83.7066	-0.7760	-6.8595	-144.2118

where d is a constant, regarded as a measure of the strength of molecular interactions between the mixing components.

The density (ρ) and viscosity (η) data of the ternary liquid mixtures at 303.15 K are presented in Table 1 which also includes the values of η^E , V^E , ΔG^{FE} and d .

The variation of ρ and η of the ternary liquid mixtures with their composition has been studied by plotting ρ and η with the mole fraction (x_1) of the first component, i.e. pyridine. The results are shown in Figs. 1-6. It is seen that the plots, in each case, are non-linear, indicating the presence of molecular interactions⁵⁻⁷. The variations of η^E

with the composition of the ternary liquid mixtures are shown in Figs. 7-9 by plotting η^E against the mole fraction (x_1) of the first component (pyridine). The values of η^E are found to be negative for all the ternary liquid mixtures under study, indicating the dominance of dispersion forces between the unlike molecules^{6,8}. So far as the variation of ΔG^{FE} with the composition of ternary liquid mixtures is concerned, the ternary liquid mixtures under discussion can be classified in the following two categories: (i) the liquid mixtures with the negative values of ΔG^{FE} , and (ii) the liquid mixtures in which ΔG^{FE} changes the sign from positive to negative.

In the ternary liquid mixtures involving benzene as the third component, the values of ΔG^{FE} have been found to be negative over the entire range of composition. The plots of ΔG^{FE} vs x_1 are shown in Figs. 10-12. The negative values of

Fig. 1. Variation of ρ with x_1 of pyridine in ternary liquid mixture of pyridine + acetone + benzene at 303.15 K.

Fig. 2. Variation of ρ with x_1 of pyridine in ternary liquid mixture of pyridine + acetone + toluene at 303.15 K.

Fig. 3. Variation of ρ with x_1 of pyridine in ternary liquid mixture of pyridine + acetone + carbon tetrachloride at 303.15 K.

ΔG^{FE} in the above ternary mixtures may be attributed to the dominance of dispersion forces due to weak intermolecular interactions followed by complex formation between the mixing molecules⁹.

The ternary liquid mixtures involving toluene or carbon

Fig. 4. Variation of η with x_1 of pyridine in ternary liquid mixture of pyridine + acetone + benzene at 303.15 K.

Fig. 5. Variation of η with x_1 of pyridine in ternary liquid mixture of pyridine + acetone + toluene at 303.15 K.

Fig. 6. Variation of η with x_1 of pyridine in ternary liquid mixture of pyridine + acetone + carbon tetrachloride at 303.15 K.

tetrachloride as the third component show the inversion in the values of ΔG^{FE} from positive to negative. The positive values of ΔG^{FE} at lower composition range indicate the presence of strong interactions between the mixing components accompanied by the complex formation. However, at higher composition range, the values of ΔG^{FE} are negative which may be attributed to the presence of dispersion forces arising out due to the dissociation of molecular complexes.

Fig. 7. Variation of η^E with x_1 of pyridine in ternary liquid mixture of pyridine + acetone + benzene at 303.15 K.

Fig. 10. Variation of ΔG^E with x_1 of pyridine in ternary liquid mixture of pyridine + acetone + benzene at 303.15 K.

Fig. 8. Variation of η^E with x_1 of pyridine in ternary liquid mixture of pyridine + acetone + toluene at 303.15 K.

Fig. 11. Variation of ΔG^E with x_1 of pyridine in ternary liquid mixture of pyridine + acetone + toluene at 303.15 K.

Fig. 9. Variation of η^E with x_1 of pyridine in ternary liquid mixture of pyridine + acetone + carbon tetrachloride at 303.15 K.

Fig. 12. Variation of ΔG^E with x_1 of pyridine in ternary liquid mixture of pyridine + acetone + carbon tetrachloride at 303.15 K.

A perusal of Table I reveals that the values of V^E vary with the composition. The values of V^E are found to be negative over the entire range of composition which may be attributed to the formation of intermolecular complexes between the mixing components. However, at the higher values of x_1 , the less negative values of V^E may be ascribed to the dissociation of molecular complexes.

The interaction parameter d has been calculated (vide eq. 6) for the ternary liquid mixtures under discussion as a function of the composition of the mixtures and the values are listed in Table 1. It is seen that the values of d vary greatly in magnitude with the composition, indicating the presence of specific interactions⁸. It is seen that the values of d are negative over the entire range of composition of the ternary liquid mixtures involving benzene or toluene as the

third component, while in the ternary liquid mixtures involving carbon tetrachloride as the third component the values change sign from negative to positive. The positive value of d indicates the presence of strong molecular interactions due to appreciable dipole-dipole and dipole-induced dipole interactions¹⁰ while the negative values of d may be attributed to dominance of dispersion type of forces¹¹ arising from the breaking of hydrogen bonds in associated components of the above ternary mixtures.

Experimental

All the chemicals used in the present study were of A.R. grade. The organic liquids were purified by the standard procedure¹² and their purities were checked by comparing their density and viscosity with those reported in literature¹³ at 303.15 K which almost agreed with the accuracy of $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4}$ g-cm⁻³ and $\pm 3 \times 10^{-3}$ mPa s, respectively.

All the ternary liquid mixtures of known composition were prepared volumetrically¹⁴ in stoppered measuring flasks. The densities were measured by using a well cleaned and dried dilatometer¹⁵ at experimental temperature 303.15 K. Viscosities of the pure liquid and their mixtures were measured using a Ostwald viscometer.

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